
Research on Handcrafted Products of the Graduation Design Course

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Abstract Students in the Continuing Education Department work during the day and study in the evening. Their time is very tight; hence, the Graduation Design Course is a big challenge for them. This article discusses the handcrafted product topics chosen by each student during the learning process of the Graduation Design Course. The students discussed their progress with their instructor and made revisions weekly. Finally, they proposed an exhibition featuring their work. It is hoped that this training can help them improve their theoretical knowledge and strengthen their practical skills. Moreover, the research results can also be used for reference in related fields.

Keywords Graduation Design Course, Handcrafted Products, Visual Design

Introduction

Graduation Design Courses need a combination of theory and practice. Likewise, it is necessary for good design to focus on data collection, material preparation, production skills learning, and the publication of results of the proposed topics. Secondly, the focal point must be design features and creativity.

Most of the students in the Continuing Education Department have work experience; therefore, they give more emphasis on practical needs when thinking of and solving problems. They improve designs based on existing conditions or create projects that are of interest to them. They are even willing to integrate their personal expertise or work in completing their designs.

Literature Review

In terms of the literature discussion on the topics related to Graduation Design Courses, some scholars believe that graduation design represents the transition from academia to industry. They encourage students to demonstrate the knowledge and skills that they have acquired during their entire education [3] [2]. The Graduation Design Course is the crystal of the higher education learning experience and is helpful in developing a student's personal, academic, and professional skills [5]. This course consolidates most of the learning results of the integration of theory and practice obtained during the teaching period and aims to equip students with better professional competence. Given the importance of the course, educational methods need to be continuously updated, developed, and regularly reviewed to meet professional requirements [4].

Secondly, too much time spent on social interaction on the Internet by students affects their ability to complete their graduation design on time and may even delay their graduation. The school pays close attention to Graduation Design Courses to reduce the student drop-out rate [1]. While advising students in their graduation design, teachers should help students choose a theme for their graduation design that suits them with regard to varying degrees of difficulty of quality and quantity, design direction, professional performance, etc., thus improving the quality of the presentation of their designs and also allowing students to graduate smoothly [7].

Recently, due to the impact of COVID-19, students have no technical barriers to online learning, but they have other problems such as difficulty concentrating and limited teacher-student interactions, which is incomparable

with the face-to-face teaching method. The Graduation Design Course also encountered similar problems in teacher-student interactions and group discussions [6].

Creative Design Process

The Graduation Design Course integrates the application of various theories and practices learned during the four years of university. It is the focus of design education. All schools have done their best to provide students with the most resources and assistance in the creative process, hoping to achieve and show outstanding results in competitions. Some hire teachers to provide guidance and strengthen students' practical ability or help them combine local cultural industries and characteristics to make design themes more suitable for business needs. This prepares new graduates for entering the workforce.

However, the objects of this research are students from the Continuing Education Department. They work during the day and take advanced studies at night. They pay their tuition fees with their salary. Hence, they have a more positive learning attitude. Only in the aspect of design professional ability, aesthetic display, and creation time do they need to be strengthened. Through student-teacher discussions, they come to an agreement that the student will independently create a graduation design according to the subject of his personal interest, and the teacher will provide support by giving necessary assistance and guidance, with the goal of successfully completing the graduation design.

Design Results

13 senior students in the Continuing Education Department were studied in this article. They independently created projects for the Graduation Design Course based on their personal interests and expertise. The themes they chose were: "Interlocking", "Uneven Snack Shop", "Candle in Your Heart", "Star Candy", "Thai Snacks", "Creative Handmade Pendant", "Nailing Love", "Fingertip Flower", "Moon Rise Flower", "Kiki's Homemade Panna Cotta", "Shell Graffiti", "Long Shiitake Mushroom", and "Dreamcatcher". Teachers conducted a professional review based on data collection, practical experimentation, discussion and revision, as well as the exhibition of the finished work. The following is the exhibition of the teaching and learning achievements of the Graduation Design Course discussed in this article (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Design results

Conclusions

Due to the pandemic, the exhibition of the creative works of students in this article could only be arranged and reviewed through separate streams. The teachers then wrote their opinions on the score sheet as feedback to the students' creation. In general, the results for the innovative research and development of this study are summarized and illustrated below:

- (1) The exhibition of achievements has design characteristics: Although students of the Continuing Education Department have limited time for making their creations in the Graduate Design Course, the overall exhibition was able to combine creative thinking and practical skills. Furthermore, it possessed deep design characteristics.
- (2) The practical results have commercial value: Most of the students in the Continuing Education Department have full-time work experience. Their product design seems to be more able to consider market needs and have more commercial value.
- (3) Interest and expertise orientation for reference: Graduation design courses often draw up general directions for each group of students to follow, but they usually encounter difficulties, such as different interests of students. The method of drawing up the theme and creating teaching methods according to the student's personal interests and expertise may be a reference for subsequent related research.
- (4) The creative theme can be further extended and developed: Students emphasize market demand and commercial value, but the design level and meaning should be further explored to make the design results more refined and complete.

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